

Learning English Language Through Literary Piece: Insights from A Survey at University Level Students in Sindh, Pakistan

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Abstract

The present study explores the role of English literature in the enhancement of four language skills and domains (vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation) among undergraduate English students in Pakistan. To do so, a qualitative approach was adopted to collect data from university students and faculty. Results of the survey showed that participants found English literature a helpful and interesting tool to learn the language better. Literature is seen as providing an authentic context for language learning and providing authentic models of language use. By utilizing the native language in order to comprehend the inner meaning of the text, reading literature assisted the learners to develop their vocabulary and analysis/interpretation skills. Furthermore, respondents believed that grammar is a dominant factor for understanding literature, and thus, should be integrated into the teaching process. Overall, literature was deemed a valuable resource in teaching communicative language.

Keywords: Literature; English Language Learning; Grammar; Genres; Language Skills

1. INTRODUCTION

The use of literature as a popular teaching technique for the development of the four language skills in English language study (reading, writing, listening and speaking) is widely discussed in the literature (Hişmanoğlu, 2005). This study focuses particularly on the use of English literature at the university level in Pakistan. Additionally, research suggests including written passages for teaching second languages or foreign languages (ibid). Furthermore, there is a necessity to take into account vocabulary and grammar issues in teaching processes (ibid). All of these insights have the potential to increase opportunities to include more literature in curricula, which can improve the language skills of learners.

2. BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

It is well known that language and literature are closely interlinked; linguists indicate this

relationship (Violetta-Irene, 2015). Brumfit and Ronald (1986) concur that literature is a companion to language, while Maley (1989) suggests that literature is a highly effective resource for language learning on account of its attributes such as universality, succinctness, relevance, diversity, fascination, cost-effectiveness, ambiguity, etc. Additionally, Sage (1987) commendably remarks that literature has the potential to be a rewarding and gripping teaching approach. Mason and Krashen (2004) likewise express that literature is a preferable means of delivery compared to the traditional language teaching methods. Through literature, learners can gain insights, presenting them with a variety of grammar, vocabulary and pronunciation. It can also provide an introduction to universal topics and the human state of mind. There are numerous techniques that can be employed to learn language using literary texts (Shahid, 2016), giving rise to an intriguing and less intimidating learning process. Consequently, being proficient in English opens up an array of opportunities that can facilitate one's lifestyle and career (Sultana & Ashrafuzzaman, 2016; Babu et al., 2014; Roshid & Webb, 2013; Ehsan et al., 2011; Coleman, 2010; Ainy, 2007).

Theories of language teaching and learning have been continuously shaped by the different perspectives of linguistics, psychology, education, and politics (Hall & Cook, 2012). Developing new methods and approaches is a challenging yet important task for foreign language teachers when instructing learners. The Communicative Approach endorses the use of real-world situations in language uptake. On the other hand, structured exercises used in the Audio-Lingual Method can adapt an overly monotonous approach to learning (Gangola, 2015). Literature is a foundation of the Grammar Translation Method, primarily utilized to read and translate literary works from the target language, to be used as models of good writing and 'illustrators of language studies' (Duff & Maley, 1990). In the past two decades, literature has further become a noteworthy tool in foreign language teaching and curriculums (Babae & Yahya, 2014; Duff & Maley, 1990).

Rationale of the study

- 1.2. Literature has become a crucial and essential component in language education methods and learning. Literature allows students to respond directly and authentically to written texts (Brumfit and Carter 1986, p. 15). The debate among language experts concerning the implementation of literature into an ESL/EFL curriculum has resulted in new educational approaches allowing more rewarding and successful teaching and learning (Sage 1987, p.1). Reading literature in the foreign language of instruction can appear intimidating and challenging (Jewett, 2017). Nevertheless, literature can immensely support language learning by facilitating the development of skills and interpretation abilities (Gangula, 2015; Lazar 1993). Furthermore, language lessons can become bright and inspiring through reading written texts, while grammar can aid in translation and provide students with worldwide topics of discussion (Violetta-Irene, 2015; Colley and Slater 1990). Incorporating literature in the class can increase students' motivation which can, in turn, lead to a stronger understanding of language components such as grammar, writing, vocabulary, and spelling (Teacher Book, 2018). However, a vast range of issues can hinder the successful integration of literature into an ESL/EFL curriculum such as limited material suitability, lack of research into the subject and, more generally, lack of objectives for the inclusion of literature (Babai and Yahya, 2014). Therefore, this study seeks to serve as an informative source of advantages

of literature and its incorporation into language curriculum at the university level in Pakistan. This article examines the importance of using literary texts and appropriate literary sources, the effectiveness of teaching strategies in language classrooms.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature has been becoming increasingly prevalent in English as a Foreign Language (EFL) classrooms in many countries in recent times (Kaşlıoğlu & Ersin, 2018). In the 1960s to 1980s period, there were questions over the role of literature in language education. The emphasis of approaches from the 1970s-80s was centered on communicative and practical language training. But in the 1980s, the significance of literature and its usage in language instruction was recognized and became a more prevalent methods (Hall, 2005; Duff & Maley, 1990). This complies with the communicative methods of teaching a second language, as it focuses on providing authentic conversations (Sanz & Fernández, 1997). Poetic elements of literature such as metaphors, similes and allusions, were noted by authors such as Brumft and Carter (1986) and Lazar (1993) to make use of language in a more general sense.

When it comes to the selection of written material for students, this should be subject to what pertains to the student's learning targets, experiences, cultural background and language level (Collie & Slater, 1987). The level of difficulty of the reading pieces should not exceed the student's capabilities. Interest, attraction and relevance are all essential components. Collie and Slater's approach to literature selection, as mentioned above, highlights the importance of taking into account these important aspects of reading.

Language teachers should use literature in the language classroom for a number of important reasons: to provide an engaging and authentic body of material, to broaden students' understanding of culture and society, to give them valuable language knowledge, and to foster personal development. According to Carter and Long (1991), there are three models for using literature which should be utilised in the language classroom. The cultural model encourages exploration of culture by exposing students to various artistic and cultural heritages through the written materials. The language model is focussed on the development of language, with a primary focus on the learners and their activities. Finally, the personal development model should be the basis for any language-learning experience, as it allows students to interpret, understand and evaluate cultural models. Through creative literature exercises and engaging activities, students can increase their understanding of culture and society, and develop a stronger language knowledge.

Maley and Duff (1992) put forward a range of proposals for teacher educators, practicing teachers and those teaching English as a second language who are interested in using written texts. Mel's strategy encouraged using written texts as a learning resource to stimulate language production. The authors also recommend teachers include groups of students for the study of literary works. In addition, Dymešová (2006) claims that written texts are valuable for teaching purposes on three levels: language (due to the various genres, registers and styles they involve), procedure (created to create a connection between students) and motivation (putting learners in a highly motivated position).

Helton et al. (1998) explains that novels have many educationally benefits. These include developing learners' imaginations, problem-solving abilities, oral and written language

proficiency, and prompting learners to engage with the reading process from the outset. Hill (1993) also put forth a three-stage approach to teaching English with literature: awareness, contact with the text, and the post-stage. This methodology provides students with the necessary background knowledge and incentive to master the language. Moreover, Clandfield and Duncan (2005) maintain that literature is an effective material for language training due to its edifying nature and the possibility of student collaboration.

4. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The research questions of this study are:

1. To what extent is literature needed to develop students' language skills?
2. How are literary works effectively used in English teaching?
3. Which genres of literature are students interested in improving their language skills?

5. METHODOLOGY

This research used a qualitative approach, gathering open-ended target information from respondents through semi-structured interviews and questionnaires created by the researchers. By doing so, the researchers were better able to understand the perspectives and feelings of the respondents (Yin, 2014). The qualitative approach employed by the researchers enabled them to gain an insight into the behaviours and attitudes of the participants, as well as the social and cultural contexts that may have influenced these (Neuman, 2003).

Samples/participants and instruments

Thirty students of English from both public and private universities were purposefully selected for this study. Six faculty members from public and private universities were also purposefully selected to assist with the research. An open-ended questionnaire and semi-structured interview schedule were developed to gather detailed information on learning English through literature. The open-ended questionnaire and interview schedule contained questions to gain further insight into the topic. Sources of open data such as interviews were also utilized to facilitate the research (Feng & Li, 2020).

<i>Sample</i>	<i>No of Respondents</i>	<i>Sampling Techniques</i>	<i>Data Collection Instruments</i>
University Students (Public)	20	Purposive	Open-ended questionnaire
University Students (Private)	20	Purposive	Open-ended questionnaire
University Teachers (Public)	05	Purposive	Semi-structured Interview Schedule
University Teachers (Private)	05	Purposive	Semi-structured Interview Schedule

6. DATA COLLECTION AND ANALYSIS

The researchers of this study employed a thematic approach to analyze the collected data, with particular focus on identifying emerging patterns. Creswell (2008) suggests the use of categorizing and subdividing the raw data into themes in order to prepare a narrative of general interpretations. During the data collection and analysis process, the researchers employed a checklist for clarification and accuracy in order to ensure the data was adequately analyzed and coded. In the interest of maintaining ethical practices, the researchers also incorporated steps to ensure ethical considerations were taken at all stages of the research.

6.1 RESULTS

The importance of learning English

The majority of the respondents (n=27) considers that English is the most essential language for communication with people from around the world. They emphasized that improving their English language skills is essential for forming and maintaining international relationships. Moreover, English proficiency has made access to higher education more accessible, both domestically and internationally, as certificates such as the IELTS and TOEFL are often required for admittance. Additionally, students recognize that this language helps them find better jobs, as English is increasingly necessary within the global job market. Furthermore, English proficiency can provide access to grants and scholarships from different countries, as well as fostering successful business transactions. Finally, students believe that English skills help them to use the Internet to stay connected, learn, conduct business, and have fun.

In addition to the practicality of learning English, students (n=18) commented that the process of learning the language is enjoyable; one respondent stated, "I like learning English. Because it helps me understand what's happening in the world every day, communicate with foreigners, get a higher education, build a good personality and find a good job."

The primary goals for learning English include higher scores on tests such as the IELTS or TOEFL, facilitating access to scholarship opportunities, and increasing CGPA scores by studying courses which require an intermediate level of English language skills (n=14). The respondents also highlighted that English is necessary for understanding English literature, and for keeping up with current world news.

Students agreed that English was an international language and that it was necessary to learn it in order to have successful careers in a global world. They stated that the main goal of learning English was to be able to effectively communicate in a competitive and intellectual world.

Most students reported that speaking is the hardest English skill, and nearly all of them found reading and writing to be the easiest. They commented that reading and writing can be done more easily since it does not require putting grammar rules into practice, something that is practiced since elementary school. On the other hand, a few found that listening was the easiest; as it provides the perfect opportunity to practice the language, allowing one to get accustomed to pronunciation and intonation.

Most agreed that literature and grammar should be studied in tandem. The reason for this is that grammatical skills is necessary to be able to fully understand the literature. Furthermore, without a basic knowledge of grammar, it can be difficult to comprehend the literature if it is approached directly. Others preferred to focus on literature over grammar for reasons such as being hard to understand the rules of grammar and think in English.

7. DISCUSSION

Several studies have concluded that incorporating literature into the ELT (English Language Teaching) classroom can be a beneficial process for enhancing students' language development (Banu, 2002; Begum et al., 2005). It has been shown to promote appreciation of different cultures, personal engagement, and personal growth (Carter & Long, 1991). Additionally, literature can improve critical thinking in secondary school learners, which is an essential component of academic success (Butler, 2006; El Kaya, 2005; Gangola, 2015).

The respondents in the aforementioned studies found learning English through literature enjoyable and mutually beneficial, as it helps them develop interpretive and analytical skills, enrich their vocabulary, as well as increase their general language awareness (Ahmed, 2007). Furthermore, it has been suggested that studying literature can lead to greater proficiency in English, as it helps learners acquire native language skills, better organize their thoughts and become creative and analytical writers (Cho et al., 2005; Ghosn, 2002; Hadaway et al., 2002; Hess, 2006; Kim, 2004; Reid, 2002). Additionally, language learners can also foster their understanding of native use of language norms and idiomatic expressions (Hall, 2005; Obediat, 1997; Shahid, 2016).

Though all four language skills are important in acquiring a new language, participants of the studies cited above reported that their primary concern related to developing their speaking ability (Alam & Ashrafuzzaman, 2018). Reading literature was noted as an effective method, as it provides an opportunity to activate learners' imagination and emotions (Babae & Yahya, 2014). Contextual reading has further been stated to play an important role in keeping new vocabularies firmly in students' memories (Alam & Ashrafuzzaman, 2018). Furthermore, most believed that learning and understanding literature depended on grammatical skills. They prefer grammar to literature in language learning, because they feel great difficulties for learners if they turn directly to literature without sufficient basic knowledge of grammar.

The majority of students read both literature and academic books, and they describe their favorite genres as fiction, poetry, and science fiction (Jewett, 2017). It is also found that novels, short stories, non-fiction texts and a mixture of different types of texts are deemed the most important literary genres. Furthermore, they overwhelmingly appreciate the opportunity of being able to read literature in their native tongue as it aids in the comprehension of the meaningfulness. Reports have revealed that reading literature in their native language is easier for most respondents (Collie & Slater, 1987). This can be attributed to being able to detect the emphasis with better precision. With regards to communicative language teaching, literature has been identified as the most efficient way to make lessons

more productive and fun (Collie & Slater, 1987). In order to achieve this, teachers commonly incorporate conversations, role plays, open discussions, creative tasks and other methods that cater to the individual needs of pupils (Collie & Slater, 1987). Other tried and tested methods of teaching language through literature include reading genre literature, conversing in English, watching English movies or shows, listening to songs, attending lectures and so on.

8. CONCLUSIONS

English serves as a foreign or second language to many countries around the world. Literature can be an effective teaching tool for learners, as it provides a deep well of authentic material. In Pakistan, literary studies are a crucial component of education, and have a powerful role to play in helping individuals to develop on a personal level. Through various forms of writing, students can expand their imaginations, build emotional intelligence, explore different cultures and understand the events of past eras.

Yet, for the most part, educational curricula are missing important goals that could define the role of literature in discouraging early school dropouts. In order to help students effectively learn written English, teachers need to make strategic use of teaching methods, activities and academic texts. Relevant source material should draw upon the learners' life experiences and evoke their dreams and feelings. To ensure a high standard of instruction, educators should undergo pre-employment and on-the-job training.

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